

Morphological Stylistic Devices through the Lens of Memetic and Literary Discourses

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ABSTRACT

Our investigation is devoted to analysing the morphological stylistic devices in memetic and literary discourse. The basic focus of the paper is the functioning of root repetition, affixational repetition, and occasional (nonce) words. Both root and affixational foregrounding of morphemes serve as the foundation for these morphological stylistic devices; moreover, this process may be carried out in two possible ways: by their reiteration or by extension of their valency.

The research attempts to highlight characteristics of both literary and memetic discourse and regards stylistic devices as a crucial feature of their similarity. Literary discourse is considered to be a communication exchange between the author and the reader, which operates as a single communication unit. In contrast, memetic discourse is regarded as user-generated internet communication, unrestricted by linguistic boundaries. Different memes, categorised by user age and social group, use morphological stylistic elements.

However, since the most well-known memes convey concepts and feelings that are generally comprehensible, it is highly likely that they can be seen as universal and do not require any particular expertise. Using morphological stylistic techniques, members of participatory culture either consciously or unconsciously adhere to literary tradition, thus preserving rhetorical legacy, even though the frequency of morphological stylistic techniques varies across literary and memetic discourses.

Keywords: affixational repetition, literary discourse, memetic discourse, occasional word, root repetition.

INTRODUCTION

This paper dwells on the notions of morphological stylistic devices in memetic discourse. Our attention focuses on three stylistic devices: root repetition, affixational repetition, and occasional words. We tend to highlight the main points of memetic discourse and literary discourse as two key points for understanding the nature of stylistic choice. The objective of our research is to gain more insight into the linguistic mechanisms of these stylistic devices within the mentioned discourses. To complete the overall picture of peculiarities of morphological stylistic devices, we gathered our samples from various sources: literary works, internet sites (Know Your Meme, Imgur), social networks (TikTok, Instagram, X), and local messenger groups (Viber, Telegram).

Literature review revealed few studies highlighting the role of morphological stylistic devices in literary and memetic discourse. In the present article, we first dwell on the notions of literary and memetic discourse, then we scrutinise morphological stylistic devices as constituents of both types of discourse.

A generally accepted definition of literary discourse has proved elusive. Literary discourse, for Batsevich (2004, p. 140), is a type of communicative activity that loses its routine nature, prompting each recipient to derive their unique meaning from it. Also, literary discourse can be seen as a communicative interaction between the text's creator and the reader, which functions as a single unit of communication (Soloviova et al. 2020, p. 214). Moreover, we point out the following idea to bolster our viewpoint: it is essential to emphasise how representational literary discourse is, by bringing the word or phrase into a much more active and reinforcing interaction, it serves to both allude to and, in a sense, echo, imitate, or embody what is conveyed (Burton & Carter, 2006, p. 270). Also, literary discourse may be influenced by the individual author's perspective – a conceptually defined imaginative framework subtly becoming more like reality (İsgandarova, 2023, p. 182).

Viewed through the lens of memetic discourse, a meme represents a communicative-pragmatic pattern of language behaviour with intertextuality at its core. There are multiple definitions of memes as “inherently unstable cultural forms” (Nissenbaum & Shifman, 2017, p. 498). In this paper, we follow our interpretation of memes as user-generated, remixed and recontextualised viral short texts, videos, or images. The term “meme” will be used throughout this article to describe a cultural information unit that spreads through social media, with its main attributes being its rapid dissemination and conciseness. Memetic discourse, which can be widely understood and is typically not limited by linguistic barriers, comprises memes as subtexts in user-generated online communication.

Our research has so far maintained that a meme is a piece of cultural knowledge that makes up memetic discourse. The practices of memetics in literary and memetic discourses are the focus of the next section.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Any language “is not a disorganised mass of sounds and symbols, but is instead an intricate web of levels, layers and links” (Simpson, 2014, p. 5). Stylistics in general and stylistic analysis in particular focus on “the phonological, lexical, grammatical, semantic, pragmatic or discursual features of texts, on the cognitive aspects involved in the processing of those features by the reader as well as on various combinations of these” (Nørgaard et al., 2010, p. 1). In our paper, we scrutinise the morphological layer of stylistic devices, which we treat as intentional use of literary and figurative tools (Lypchanko-Kovachyk & Radyk, 2018, p. 145) that are conceived and perceived as “a deviation from the generally used norms of linguistic communication” (Babelyuk, 2011, p. 8).

By drawing on the notion of morphemic stylistic device, Kukharenko (2014, pp. 21-22) showed that only three ways to foreground a morpheme exist, all resulting in the creation of the stylistic device. Following this line, the first way is to repeat the morpheme in one short context. Notably, both root and affixational morphemes may be reiterated; thus, the stylistic devices of **root repetition** and **affixational repetition** emerge.

Moving on to the second principle, it is stated that a more sophisticated way to foreground a morpheme is to extend its valency. Generally, the term “valency” is applied to lexemes as “the bonding potential of words and phrases in sentences, usually in relation to the verb as a syntactic nucleus” (Hartmann & James, 2002, p. 153). However, the morpheme has its own combinatory power as “the smallest meaningful unit of morphological analysis” (Bauer et al., 2015, p.14); furthermore, they can be seen as “the minimal meaningful units that are used to form words” (Lieber, 2009, p. 32).

Continuing our examination of the features of morphemes, we should note that morphemes may carry different types of meaning: **lexical** (root morphemes convey semantic meaning), **grammatical** (inflectional morphemes indicate various forms of a word), and **derivational** (derivational morphemes are used to form new words) (Manova, 2020, p. 5). Below, we will analyse what types of morphemes participate in memetic practices.

Thirdly, non-existent nonce words appear due to the irregular combination of morphemes. Consequently, new words, **occasional words**, are coined – not to enrich the vocabulary on a constant basis, but to name the unnamed in an entertaining way. We shall observe the peculiarities of these three stylistic devices in memetic discourse.

ROOT REPETITION

This part of our study is focused on identifying and evaluating the role of root repetition in the memetic practices. In this article, the term **root repetition** will refer to the reiteration of the root morpheme, which emphasises the key notion of the text, drawing our attention to this particular concept. This stylistic device is realised when one root morpheme appears in two or more words used in one short context, as in the example below (pic. 1): the words TIRE and TIRING have the same root morpheme cognate to TIRE and reveal the physical and emotional state of the meme character: “to begin to feel as if you have no energy and want to rest or go to sleep, or to make someone feel this way” (Cambridge University Press, n.d.).

I'm always _____
in the morning.

Picture 1. Repetition of the root morpheme TIRE

Creators of memes utilise words with the reiterated root relatively often, since this stylistic device does not create difficulties in grasping the main idea of the message. On the contrary, it facilitates the key concept perception by stressing it. The message in the meme below (pic. 2) runs as follows: 5000 YEARS OF ACCUMULATED HUMAN **KNOWLEDGE AND KNOWHOW**. CHATGPT. Human intellectual heritage is highlighted by the root repetition of the morpheme **KNOW** – and opposed by the newest technical development of a compelling and extremely popular large language model ChatGPT that diminishes human achievements and makes them even obsolete, as is highlighted by the stance of the meme template (Disaster Girl), where a girl looks right into the camera with an evil smirk:

Picture 2. Disaster Girl in the role of ChatGPT

An effect of hyperbolisation may emerge due to the employment of this stylistic device, because the repetition of the same notion within one context, usually a sentence, may sound absurdly intensive, as in the following example (pic. 3): TOM CRUISE!! PUT THE **DUSH** IN THE **DUSHBAG**! The derogatory nominations are used here: DUSH, which is an incorrect form of the word DOUCHE “an unpleasant person” (Cambridge University Press, n.d.), and DUSHBAG, correctly DOUCHEBAG “an unpleasant person” (ibid.). These synonymous offensive nouns are still understandable to the addressee, notwithstanding their incorrectness, since they are homophones of the real slang words. They hyperbolise the dominant negative emotional stance of the meme. We may also suggest that this meme demonstrates such a figure of speech as **adnomination** – juxtaposition of similar roots or speech sounds, “the repetition of words with a change in letter or sound” (Cagampang, n.d.). Furthermore, adnomination is regarded as a literary technique that produces a particular sound and effect in a text by repeating words that share a root word or by echoing the sound of one word in another within the exact phrase (Ultius, n.d.).

Picture 3. Root repetition with the effect of hyperbolisation

Moreover, contamination of morphological stylistic devices with other devices is common in memetic discourse. Root repetition may co-function not only with

hyperbole, as in the instance above, but also with a range of other devices. It is illustrated in the next meme (pic. 4):

Picture 4. Root repetition with emotive climax

The text I LOVED THE **WITCH** (2015) AND THE **WITCHER** (2019), SO I CAN'T WAIT FOR THE **WITCHEST** (2023) illustrates the use of the root repetition of the morpheme **WITCH** and an occasional word **WITCHEST** that mimics the superlative degree of an adjective or adverb, incorrectly applied to the noun, as well as three parallel constructions, each next being more emotionally intense and logically more important – thus forming the stylistic device of a three-step emotive climax. Additionally, this example perfectly illustrates the use of **polypopton** – employment of the same root in different grammatical forms, “the rhetorical repetition within the same sentence of a word in a different case, inflexion, or voice or of etymologically related words in different parts of speech” (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.). Similarly, polypopton is seen as a recurrence of words that share a root (Corbett, 1998, p. 438). Bright examples of polypopton may be found in both texts of olden times, as in Shakespeare’s play and in modern times, as in Kennedy’s speech:

*“The Greeks are **strong**, and **skilful** to their **strength**,*

***Fierce** to their **skill**, and to their **fierceness** valiant”* (Shakespeare, Troilus and Cressida, I, i, 7-8);

“*Their **blood bleeds** the nation of its sanguine assurance. Not as a call to **battle**, though **embattled** we are*” (John F. Kennedy, Inaugural Address (Corbett, 1998, p.438).

Different types of discourse “often display a high degree of stylistic dexterity, such that it would be wrong to view dexterity in language use as exclusive to canonical literature” (Simpson, 2014, p. 3). Stylistic colouring is likely an inherent feature of both memetic and literary discourses. And we can observe that root repetition is used in literary discourse, though less frequently than in memetic discourse. The linguistic mechanism of creating this stylistic device and its functions is similar in both types of discourse. Below, we provide examples from classical literature that illustrate striking cases of root repetition:

“*Our **stitching** and **unstitching** has been naught*” (William Butler Yeats, *Adam's Curse*).

“*Love is not love*

*Which **alters** when it **alteration** finds,*

*Or bends with the **remover** to **remove**”* (William Shakespeare, *Sonnet 116*).

“*No end to the **withering** of **withered** flowers,*

*To the movement of **pain** that is **painless** and motionless,*

*To the **drift** of the sea and the **drifting** wreckage”* (Thomas Stearns Eliot, *The Dry Salvages*).

The frequency with which this device appears in memetic discourse is relatively higher, as it creates concepts which could be shared. Generating new notions and enhancing existing ones, this mechanism creates emotional saturation and highlights the effects desired by memetic discourse participants.

AFFIXATIONAL REPETITION

The second phenomenon in our study is affixational repetition. The phrase **affixational repetition** will be used in this paper to describe the reiteration of prefixes and/or suffixes, foregrounding some shades of meaning. Traditionally, several subtypes of affixational repetition are described:

- **prefixational repetition** is observed when the prefix is repeated two or more times within one short context;
- **suffixational repetition** happens when the suffix is repeated;
- **mixed affixational repetition** is based on the repetition of both the prefix and suffix, only the root morpheme changes;
- **chain affixation** appears when the affix is repeated, forming a gradation with the effect of accumulated emotional and logical importance;
- **paronomastic affixation** includes not only the repetition of the affix, but also builds up the effect of paronomastic attraction of the engaged words.

Generally speaking, affixational repetition is not as vivid as root repetition, requiring more effort from the meme creator without resulting in a considerable effect. It also requires a broader context, frequently not supplied by a one- or two-word meme. Consequently, this stylistic device is rarely used in memetic discourse. We have found several examples of suffixal repetition, mainly with the inflectional suffix *-ing*, as seen in pictures 5 and 6. The general use of affixes in the English language aligns with this memetic peculiarity since inflectional suffixes constitute 97% of all cases, leaving only 3% to derivational suffixes.

Picture 5. Suffixal repetition with the inflectional suffix *-ing*

Picture 6. Suffixal repetition with the inflectional suffix *-ing*

The example of prefixal repetition was selected where the prefix *un-* appears 3 times: **UNLOCKABLE**, **UNLOCKED**, **UNABLE**. Here, affixational repetition is combined with root repetition of morphemes **LOCK** and **ABLE** (pic. 7):

Does unlockable mean "able to be unlocked" or "unable to be locked"?

Picture 7. Prefixal repetition with the prefix *un-*

One example of paronomastic affixation (out of very few) was selected, where the suffix *-ish* is used to create play on words: AROUND 1.3...ISH; BY NOON-ISH; SPIKE JONZE-ISH, LANCE-ACORD-ISH, PEGGY SIROTA-ISH; ISH; ISH:

Picture 8. Paronomastic affixation with the suffix *-ish*

The suffix is employed to name a sum of money, time, and the style of famous creators, and it even serves as a separate word. Today, *-ish* is included in dictionaries as an adverb with the meaning of “used for saying that something is

not completely true or exactly right” (Cambridge University Press, n.d.), having partially lost the status of a morpheme and developing its own lexical meaning. This process of **degrammaticalisation** affected only a few affixes in the English language, such as *pro-*, *con-*, *anti-*, *-esque*, *-ism*.

Literary discourse makes greater use of affixational repetition, owing to its broader textual scope, as the examples below demonstrate:

“*To watch a white gull take*

A bit of bread thrown up into the air;

*Now gyri**ng** down and per**ni**ng there” (William Butler Yeats, *Demon and Beast*)*

“*Troubled, wilder**ed**, and forlorn,*

*Dark, benight**ed**, travel-worn,*

Over many a tangle spray,

*All heart-bro**ke**” (William Blake, *A Dream*)*

“*Thus let me live, un**se**en, un**kn**own;*

*Thus un**la**mented let me die;*

Steal from the world, and not a stone

*Tell where I lie” (Alexander Pope, *Ode on Solitude*)*

Interestingly, several titles of books contain this stylistic device, as in *Unseen, Unheard, Unknown* by Sarah Hamilton-Byrne or *Homeless Isn't Hopeless: A Remarkable Journey of Hope and Humor* by William Laney.

We cannot overlook one of the most vivid examples of affixational repetition in a passage from the letter from Sol Lewitt to his fellow artist Eva Hesse, where the ING suffix appears numerous times, stressing the intensity of the effort exerted:

“Just stop thinking, worrying, looking over your shoulder wondering, doubting, fearing, hurting, hoping for some easy way out, struggling, grasping, confusing, itching, scratching, mumbling, bumbling, grumbling, humbling, stumbling, numbling, rumbling, gambling, tumbling, scumbling, scrambling, hitching, hatching, bitching, moaning, groaning, honing, boning, horse-shitting, hair-splitting, nit-picking, piss-trickling, nose sticking, ass-gouging, eyeball-poking, finger-pointing, alleyway-sneaking, long waiting, small stepping, evil-eyeing, back-scratching, searching, perching, besmirching, grinding, grinding, grinding away at yourself. Stop it and just DO!” (Almquist, n.d.)

It should be noted that this text was masterfully performed by Benedict Cumberbatch, highlighting the meaning of the reiterated morpheme through visual and acoustic modes (2019).

Affixational repetition is one of the rarest but most vivid morphological stylistic devices. It can be seen as a powerful tool since it creates emphasis through rhythm. This, in turn, helps communicate emotional state to other members of participatory culture and share it with participants of memetic discourse.

OCCASIONAL WORDS (OCCASIONALISMS, NONCE WORDS)

The third part of our investigation dwells on the **occasional words (occasionalisms or nonce words)** created for one occasion only. They appear when an exact word to name the desired phenomenon does not exist in the language, for amusement and entertainment, or, maybe, both. A nonce word is “coined and used apparently to suit one particular occasion. Nonce words are sometimes used independently by different writers and speakers, but they are not adopted into general use” (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.). Thus, “creation of “incorrect” (according to word formation and combinatory

power) new words, “darkened” in form and meaning to give freshness and brightness to the message, brings to life occasional words” (Karpenko, Neklesova, 2024, p. 539). Such linguistic improvisation demonstrates a certain degree of unpredictability and novelty in coinages, resulting in heightened expressiveness and the ability to go viral for the meme.

Occasional words are assembled as a linguistic puzzle from usual word-forming elements so that “their interaction in a particular derivative may result in the expansion of internal valence and pushes it beyond the language norm” (Hreshchuk, 2021, p. 79). In the following pages, we will attempt to analyse this process of naming the unnamed and combining the uncombinable in memetic discourse.

Some concepts by sheer luck (or, rather, unluck) just happen to have no word to name them, since this word was not required for some cultural or historical reason. However, when it appears, its fresh linguistic expressiveness is quite powerful, especially if it is coined for one particular entertaining experience, as it happened to a Finnish word *kalsarikännit*, which approximately means *to get drunk alone in one’s own house wearing only underwear* (Kielitoimiston sanakirja, n.d. (pic. 9)). This recreational activity is less popular with English native speakers, evidently, since no similar or semantically close word exists in English. Still, the concept turned out to be appealing, thus, transferring to memes, naming the unnamed:

Picture 9. Finnish nonce word, *kalsarikännit*

A brighter example of occasional words is presented in the next meme (pic. 10), where a group of koalas is called KOALITION and a group of opossums OPOSSITION. Here we also deal with the play on words, pun, based on the homophones *koalition::coalition* and *opossition::opposition*:

Picture 10. Occasional words forming a pun

The morphemes that are usually not combined attract the reader's attention through the unexpected word-building turn, as in the example **YOU CAN NOT UNSAY MEAN WORDS**. The verb *say* is not used with this negative prefix in modern English, and the word *unsay*, once a regular part of the English vocabulary, is considered obsolete now (Oxford English Dictionary, n.d.), so it may be easily perceived as an occasional word:

Picture 11. UNSAY as an occasional word

The similar process of combining the uncombinable is best illustrated by the meme TIME FOR THANKS-TAKING (pic. 12). The occasionalism here is constructed by analogy with the name of the American holiday *Thanksgiving*, featuring the main dish of this holiday, a turkey, in a hitman’s attire and armed accordingly:

Picture 12. Analogy with the holiday *Thanksgiving*

Here, the element *giving* that implies *giving prayers for God’s blessings* turns into its antonym *taking* with the implication of *taking revenge for being killed*

and served for food. Again, the stylistic device of pun appears here as well, causing a desired humorous effect.

If the example above had a picture as a necessary context, without which the meme would have remained almost incomprehensible, then in the meme below (pic. 13), the visual element is optional, since the linguistic context suffices. The proverbial phrase *When life gives you lemons, make lemonade* is altered into **WHEN LIFE GIVES YOU DEMONS MAKE DEMONADE:**

Picture 13. Nonce word, *demonade*, based on the known proverb

The paronomastic attraction of two words, *lemon* and *demon*, hence, *lemonade* and *demonade*, allowed to alter the form of the proverb, thus creating a play on words, the stylistic device of violation of a phraseological unit, which, together with the occasional word, produces a distinct humorous effect. The same effect is achieved in the following meme, where an occasional word **CORONIALS** (the generation of Covid-19 or Coronavirus pandemic times) is coined by analogy with the term *millennials* (or Generation Y) (pic. 14):

Picture 14. Occasional word *coronials* coined by analogy with *millennials*

From another perspective, in literary discourse, this stylistic device appears occasionally due to its expressive potential. As a rule, such nonce words are used in groups to create a specific style, dialect, or idiolect, as in a nonsense poem by Lewis Carroll or an idiolect of a Giant in Roald Dahl's book for children:

“ ’Twas **brillig**, and the **slithy toves**

Did gyre and gimble in the **wabe**:

All **mimsy** were the **borogoves**,

And the **mome raths outgrabe**” (Lewis Carroll. *Jabberwocky* from *Through the Looking-Glass*).

“When a ladybird is walking across a leaf, I is hearing her feet going **clumpety-clumpety-clump** like giants’ footsteps”; “You think I is **swizzfiggling** you?” (Roald Dahl, *The BFG*).

CONCLUSION

The analysed morphological stylistic devices show different frequencies of occurrence in memetic discourse: occasional words dominate, root repetition ranks second, and affixational repetition is the least frequent. This tendency

differs from literary discourse, where the dominant position is taken by affixational repetition, followed by root repetition, with occasional words being presented by isolated examples. This discrepancy might be attributed to the distinct modes of representation: literary texts are characterised by an extended verbal context, whereas memes employ a two-dimensional format, combining limited verbal material with visual imagery or sound.

Furthermore, the author of a literary work is typically an educated individual who creates art for a reader with a particular cultural thesaurus and educational background. In contrast, memes circulate among ordinary people at both ends of the communicative chain. To paraphrase Abraham Lincoln, memes are made “by the people, of the people, for the people”, thus forming a participatory culture where every person may simultaneously be both the creator and the recipient.

Morphological stylistic devices can be found in various memes, which are classified by age and social group. Though it is highly likely that the most well-known memes are universal and don't require any special knowledge, as they communicate universally understandable ideas and emotions. Employing morphological stylistic devices, members of participatory culture follow literary tradition, deliberately or intuitively. Although the frequency of morphological stylistic devices differs in memetic and literary discourses, this rhetorical heritage is maintained, and the legacy is flourishing.

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